

Natural features and difference of English and Uzbek foods

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Annotation

This article is about information about difference and similarities between two cultures which are Uzbek and English. You can find name of meals and foods.

Key words: recipes, traditions, customs, cuisine, meal

Uzbek food is among the most delicious in the world, for over the centuries it absorbed and adapted the best recipes from neighboring cultures to create a flavorful and satisfying cuisine. A highlight of Uzbek cuisine in comparison with its Central Asian neighbors is that they enjoy not only meat dishes but vegetables and salads too. In fact, Uzbek fruits and vegetables are so good that they are exported to other countries. This was not always the case, however. Until the 19th century the local diet consisted mostly of meat, dough, milk and cereals. Meat, particularly beef and lamb, remain the basis of the local diet today. Horse meat is also enjoyed as a delicacy, while poultry is less popular. Fish dishes are rather uncommon in this double-landlocked nation. Uzbek food is rich in seasonings which accentuate the flavor of the dishes and leave a pleasant aftertaste. Uzbeks are very hospitable people who will never let guests go hungry: First, because it will not be easy to decline a true invitation; second, because the Uzbek table is usually replete with food; and finally, because after a filling meal you are likely to be sent home with leftovers. Kebabs, called shashlik, are one of the main meat dishes in Uzbekistan. Shashlik comes in many varieties, including ground beef (lyulya), mutton, beef, chicken, liver and vegetable. Fibre: natural prebiotic for gut health Over 80% of the cells which make up our immune system are located in the wall of our intestine. Gut bacteria here support a well-developed immunity. Fibre is a type of carbohydrate that can't be digested in the small intestine, passing instead to the colon (large intestine). Here it provides fuel for billions of these beneficial gut bacteria, which ferment it to produce many compounds essential for our everyday metabolism and the correct functioning of our

gut wall. Collectively known as our 'Microbiome' and with 150x our own genetic makeup, our microbiome is to be nurtured! Our gut bacteria also have an important role activating antioxidants in some foods which are also beneficial in boosting our immunity. Skin-on Veg and Fruit, Nuts, Seeds, grains like Oats and other Wholemeal Cereals, Brown & Wild Rice, Wholemeal Pasta, Quinoa, Beans, Peas and Pulses like Kidney & Fava beans, Chickpeas & Lentils. Fermented Foods: natural probiotics for Gut Health These foods have been fermented so are already brimming with good bacteria and their beneficial products of fermentation as described above. Bio-live yogurt, Yakult, Actimel, Marmite, Vegemite, Sourdough (bacteria inactivated on cooking but beneficial fermented products still present), Blue cheese. Less well known but wonderful! Sauerkraut, Kimchi, Miso & Kefir – an ancient fermented milk drink (meaning 'Live Long' in Turkish) bursting with billions of beneficial bacteria and yeasts. Now being made with British milk – UK suppliers below.

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